

**Youth
Goals**

EUYPD9

**ENGAGING TOGETHER FOR A
SUSTAINABLE AND INCLUSIVE EUROPE**

Implementation Phase Report

Compiled by Ondřej Bárta & Dan
Moxon, People Dialogue and Change
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National Working Groups

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Introduction

This is an implementation report of the 9th Cycle of the European Union Youth Dialogue (EUYD) overseen jointly by the Trio Presidency of France, the Czech Republic, and Sweden. This implementation report was first outlined in the 9th Cycle EUYD Toolkit prepared and presented under the French Presidency of the Council of the European Union. Overall, the implementation of the European Youth Goals #10 and #3 will be reflected as results of the 9th Cycle of the EUYD in different areas and on local, regional, national and European levels, with the overarching title “**Engaging together for a sustainable and inclusive Europe**”. The two chosen European Youth Goals aim at “*Achieving a society in which all young people are environmentally active, educated and able to make a difference in their everyday lives*” and “*Enabling and ensuring the inclusion of all young people in society*”. The TRIO considers **intergenerational dialogue** to be a tool that facilitates not only the involvement of young people in decision-making and policymaking and thus strengthens their participation in democratic processes, but also meaningful and facilitated sharing of views between young people and other generations.

The 9th Cycle EUYD Toolkit paved the way for the National Working Groups (NWGs) to identify changes that happened as a result of the 9th Cycle of the EUYD (i.e., what impacts and changes took place as a result of the NWG implementation activities within the 9th Cycle of the EUYD, **in the five key domains of the 9th Cycle of the EUYD, namely: (a) Information and Education, (b) Action and Empowerment, (c) Governance, (d) Mobility and Solidarity, and (e) Access to Infrastructure**. The 9th Cycle EUYD Toolkit also provided the NWGs with a template through which the data were reported back to the EUYD Steering Group in February 2023.

All in all, 28 National Working Groups (NWGs) from 26 EU Member States submitted the implementation reporting data, namely:

- | | |
|---|--------------------|
| • Austria (AT) | • Greece (GR) |
| • Belgium German-speaking Community (BE-DE) | • Hungary (HU) |
| • Belgium French Community (BE-FR) | • Ireland (IE) |
| • Belgium Flemish Community (BE-FL) | • Italy (IT) |
| • Bulgaria (BG) | • Lithuania (LT) |
| • Croatia (HR) | • Latvia (LV) |
| • Cyprus (CY) | • Luxembourg (LU) |
| • Czech Republic (CZ) | • Malta (MT) |
| • Denmark (DK) | • Netherlands (NL) |
| • Estonia (EE) | • Poland (PL) |
| • Finland (FI) | • Portugal (PT) |
| • France (FR) | • Slovakia (SK) |
| • Germany (DE) | • Slovenia (SI) |
| | • Spain (ES) |
| | • Sweden (SE) |

Note: Country abbreviations are listed as they are used throughout this report to refer to the NWG origin.

This implementation report presents analyses of the data provided by the NWGs above. The analyses took place in February and March 2023, they summarise and provide insights into the two main areas of the implementation reporting, namely the range of implementation activities, and the impacts identified as a result of the implementation activities of the 9th Cycle of the EUYD.

The report aims at supporting the next steps in the 9th Cycle EUYD, most notably the EU Youth Conference taking place in Växjö, Sweden in March 2023 (EUYC Växjö). Within the framework of the EUYC Växjö, the report is to be disseminated and presented, and serve as a basis for further debates of the EUYC Växjö participants.

1. Implementation Strategies

Almost all of the 28 NWGs which submitted the implementation phase term report provided information on the implementation activities they used to support the 9th Cycle of the EUYD. This chapter provides summaries and examples of these implementation activities which can be summarised in the following categories:

- **Presenting the consultation results to the general public.**
- **Presenting and debating the consultation results with policymakers.**
- **Educating relevant stakeholders.**
- **Implementing various lobbying activities.**
- **Developing tools to support Youth Goals implementation.**
- **Implementing or supporting regional or local youth dialogue activities.**
- **Utilizing research to gain further knowledge on the domains defined by Youth Goals linked to the cycle.**

Almost all NWGs reported using some form of presenting the results of the national consultation processes to the general public. The forms varied greatly, as can be seen from the list below illustrated by some examples listed by the NWGs:

- Press conferences,
- Online publishing
 - *“Croatian Youth Network (CYN) created 1 digital brochure and 5 different infographics about the implementation of the results of EUYD 9.” (HR)*
- Social media
 - *“Four ambassadors created account in Instagram and TikTok, made video (more than 700 views), stories, posts to inform about climate change and how to be more sustainable in daily life.” (LV)*
- Webinars
 - *“We have organized three different webinars with our youth delegates where we have presented the EU Youth Dialogue in general and cycle 9 in particular.” (SE)*
- Podcasts
 - *“We have produced six episodes of our podcast exclusively about cycle 9 of the EU Youth Dialogue where our youth delegates have talked about the cycle in general and its themes in particular.” (SE)*
- Videos
 - *“Creation of 3 explanatory videos about the COP Biodiversity by young members of the Youth Dialogue Team to raise awareness about this Summit.” (BE-FR)*
- Public debates
 - *“3 debates were organised by youth delegates in the two Danish democracy festivals: People’s Meeting (Folkemødet) and Political Festival of Europe. Furthermore, YDs participated in 9 debates in Folkemødet and talked from there on nationally televised news” (DK)*
- Games and contests
 - *“We organised a number of events and activities which centred around the deck of cards as a tool for enhancing participation and empowerment of young people.” (IE)*
 - *“A national contest on the topic of “My Youth Goal Story” that was mainstreamed through digital and sustainable approach.” (HR)*
- Practice-oriented events and information points

- *“In collaboration with Fridays For Future, organised a second hand clothing trade point in the street, in order to claim for responsible consumption.” (ES)*
- *“The Andalucian Embassy organised an information point in collaboration with Corresponsales Juveniles from Andalucía in order to promote the program.” (ES)*
- Conference inputs at various events
 - *“Presentation of the EU Youth Dialogue at the kick-off event for the National Action Plan on Child and Youth Participation.” (DE)*
- Multiplier events
 - *“We have implemented a session with young multipliers. In this session, young people were presented with the results from the auscultation sessions which gave them the tools to debate youth goals and implement them.” (PT)*

Almost all of the NWGs also presented results of the 9th Cycle of the EUYD also to various policymakers during different events, such as ad hoc meetings, panel discussions, round tables, conferences, participation in working groups, seminars, online events, informal meetings (e.g., picnics, breakfasts, etc.), and in some cases these processes were supported directly by the state bodies, e.g.:

“Ministry of Education and science (MES) sent information about consultations results to every ministry (and other departments in MES) to inform and ask which suggestions from youth other ministry’s plan to implement. MES informed youth workers in municipalities and NGOs (more than 200 recipients) about consultation results, best practices and created visuals for social network with youth suggestions in this topic.” (LV).

Policymakers included national, regional, and local level actors.

Almost all of the NWGs also implemented some educational activities on the topic of the EUYD9 cycle, targeted a range of different stakeholders. The following target groups can be found in the implementation efforts of the NWGs linked to education:

- Young people in general
- Specific groups of young people, e.g.,
 - *“Four Vidzeme region ambassadors decided to make an event in Valmiera SOS Children's Village (a charity organization that has been developing and supporting SOS families for children who have been left without their parental care). Main idea of the event was to inform 34 youngsters from SOS village how to take part in different mobilities events mostly in Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps programmes.” (LV)*
- (Youth) organisations, e.g.,
 - *“Education was an important method to share knowledge among the youth with the help of stakeholders within the youth sector and civil society in Hungary connected to the cycle. Besides the education of youth individuals, sharing knowledge about possibilities for better organization work of youth organizations also was in focus during these activities.” (HU)*
- Youth workers, e.g.,
 - *“Training for trainers was implemented with an aim of strengthening and widening the pool of trainers for EUYD process.” (HR)*
- Teachers, e.g.,
 - *“We also spoke to a group of teachers to emphasize the importance of climate education.” (BE-FL)*

When it comes to the forms of the implemented educational activities, these vary greatly, as can be seen from the list below illustrated by some examples listed by the NWGs, with apparent prevalence of non-formal learning methodologies:

- Hands-on learning events, e.g.,
 - *“EGEA-Tartu members went to Käsmu to increase the knowledge of their active members in the field of climate change and to visit the coast of Northern Estonia to see first-hand the consequences of climate change.”* (EE)
- Simulations, e.g.,
 - *“Some of our activities included simulations of young people’s meetings with decision-makers. The topics were on real-life sustainability issues in Bulgaria regarding transition from coal to clean energy sources.”* (BG)
- Information exchange platforms, e.g.,
 - *“Organisation of a Cycle of meetings on Climate and Social Justice. The aim was to create a space for information and exchange for young people, led by experts in the field.”* (BE-FR)
- Workshops, e.g.,
 - *“Our workshops focused on presenting the results of consultations and discussing with youth workers, educators, volunteers and young people about quality resources and information on sustainability in formal and non-formal education and beyond.”* (CZ)
- Visits of educational facilities, e.g.,
 - *“We organized a visit to the Museum for Circular Economy (a pop-up museum in Antwerp, opened by a 25-year old). This was to inform and inspire young people.”* (BE-FL)
- Seminars, e.g.,
 - *“The Maltese National Working Group has a strong relationship with both the National Youth Agency and the National Youth Council and in this regard in collaboration with the Ministry for the Environment, Energy and Enterprise, the National Youth Agency and the National Youth Council organised in seminar entitled ‘Youths discuss the future sustainability of the Maltese islands’ focusing on the he recently published Malta’s Sustainable Development Strategy for 2050. During this seminar members of the MT NWG together with SDG Youth Champions and other youth workers who were involved in the 9th cycle of EUYD and officers from the Ministry facilitated workshops whereby provided young people youth friendly information about the about the policy document and was in its consultation process so that young participants could give feedback on the document.”* (MT)
- Human libraries, e.g.,
 - *“Human Library Alicante: during the III Meeting for Embassies (Alicante, September 2022), we organised an activity to give visibility to the life story of different people belonging to vulnerable groups.”* (BG)
- Study visits, e.g.,
 - *“Youth from rural areas and club leaders from Estonian 4H took a study trip to Tallinn.”* (EE)
- Residential trainings, e.g.,
 - *“A weekend-long education and empowerment training for our EUYD ambassadors (called “Jump Team”) and EU youth delegates.”* (DE)
- Ad hoc conferences, e.g.,

- *“We organised a three-day conference “young voices for action”. Purpose was to immerse this group in the process of policy making. How could they make their voices heard, how could they influence policies that impacts them, were questions that were answered to.” (BE-FL)*
- Ad hoc inputs at other conferences, e.g.,
 - *“During the “Youth Convention” 80 youngsters between 13 and 30 met for workshops in the Chamber of Deputies (National Parliament) in the morning whilst presenting the results in the afternoon to the politicians and ministers. Except for one or two exceptions in one or two workshops, the topics of the past editions had always been related to the Youth Goals since 2019.” (LU)*
- National youth conferences, e.g.,
 - *“CYN was co-organizer of a Youth conference in Šibenik, in November 2022. Possibilities for young people within the EYD 2022 were presented, the implementation of the results of consultations with young people was discussed within the framework of EUYD 9 at the local level. (...) The national EUYD conference is planned for the beginning of April 2023, preparational and organizational activities are in progress.” (HR)*
- Networking platforms, e.g.,
 - *“Name of the project: Balkan Women Coalition. Goal of the project aims to create a stable and multinational network of institutions and organizations from the Balkan region, in order to develop qualifications and help women, especially young women with fewer opportunities, in the business field.” (GR)*
- Networking events, e.g.,
 - *“This meeting was aimed to exchange experiences of (meaningful) youth participation in the respective countries of the members and to compare Dutch/European examples with the experiences and examples of the YAC-members.” (NL)*

Some of the NWGs also implemented various lobbying and advocacy activities, such as:

- Encouraging and supporting young people in lobbying activities, e.g.,
 - *“External experts were also invited and encouraged young people to do a lot of lobbying through various channels.” (BE-DE)*
 - *“Youth ambassadors from Zemgale and Latgale regions, (8 youngsters) decide to work on events that bring together youth and decision makers. They organised events based on method “Coffee with politicians”.” (LV)*
- Seeking commitment from policymakers, e.g.,
 - *“As part of the advocacy work following the official Advice on environmental education, meetings with politicians (March-April-May) will be organized and commitments will be sought.” (BE-FR)*
- Organising direct lobbying events between youth and policymakers, e.g.,
 - *“Forum des Jeunes will organise a policy dialogue between 30 young people and the Minister of Youth. Different types of commitment will be addressed (non-formal/associative and formal/political) and the objective is to formulate recommendations to enhance the involvement of young people in the decision-making process. The Minister will be asked to respond to the youth demands.” (BE-FR)*
- Directly feeding youth voices into policymaking processes, e.g.,

- *“We agreed to collaborate on organising focus groups to update the Czech Republic 2030 strategic framework. This is a cross-sectoral document, framing other strategic documents at national, regional and local level.” (CZ)*
- Feeding youth voices into election debates, e.g.,
 - *“We have included these topics in the programme that we have published for the upcoming governmental discussions in Finland (Parliament elections).” (FI)*
- Strengthening positions of the National Youth Councils in policymaking, e.g.,
 - *“The NYC will participate in a policy decision making process on Flemish level concerning environmental health care.” (BE-FL)*
 - *“The national youth council had meetings with all newly formed ministries of the government and the ideas of the young people collected, directly or indirectly, also during the activities of the youth dialogue (activities in high schools and picnics for sustainability) were presented to the ministers.” (SI)*

Some of the NWGs also develop tools to support reaching Youth Goals, for example:

- *“Ambassadors from Kurzeme region decided to make guidelines for municipalities how to support youth councils and to create youth councils in municipality they come from.” (LV)*
- *“We are developing a tool to help facilitate intergenerational dialogue.” (NL)*
- *“Student governments will be provided with methodologies to increase public engagement and learn community organisation and maintenance practices with the help of our experts.” (HU)*

Some of the NWGs also implemented or supported regional or local youth dialogue activities which then feed into regional or local policymaking processes, for example:

- *“We organized Two regional dialogue events (in Vienna and Lower Austria) with a regional decision maker about the consultation outcomes and the relevance for their federal state. The dialogue included discussions about the topic “Information and Education”.” (AT)*
- *“The platform Rural Youth within Local Action Groups, a member of our NWG, have started a structured dialogue in the regions.” (CZ)*
- *“Local dialogue event on “Hamburg and Europe in your hands” in Hamburg; Local dialogue event on energy crises in Leipzig. (...) Dialogue/advocacy event in Berlin giving young people a voice in the political sphere.” (DE)*
- *“Paseillos universitarios: local consultation in University of Granada (September 2022) about sustainability and inclusion.” (ES)*

And lastly, some NWGs utilize research to gain further knowledge on various sub-topics of the Youth Goals, and to support consultations, lobbying, and eventually also policymaking, for example:

- *“We acknowledge that feedback is important in the field of good governance. We have complemented five representative surveys with a focus group survey per region, in order to get a comprehensive picture of the current views, concerns and suggestions of youth individuals.” (HU)*
- *“We have done research about how well the Swedish youth politics lives up to the European youth politics and written up a report about this. This report is yet to be presented at a forthcoming event.” (SE)*

2. Impacts across the EUYD9 Subthemes

This section summarises impacts collected and submitted by NWGs in the five target areas, namely:

- **Information and Education**
- **Action and Empowerment**
- **Governance**
- **Mobility and Solidarity**
- **Access to Infrastructure**

2.1.1. Summary of Impacts in Information and Education

The Toolkit of the 9th Cycle of the EUYD describes this subtheme as follows: *“Climate change is a complex issue and as such spans different scientific areas, connects different policy domains, links to many areas of human production and consumption, and can be difficult to fully grasp in all its implications. Young people should have access to youth-friendly information sources, and opportunities to learn about the nature and causes of climate change, and its relation to social inequalities all around the world. These learning opportunities and resources should be based within the formal education as well as in non-formal and informal learning contexts. These resources and opportunities need to be accessible, inclusive and reach out to young people from all walks of life. They should also focus on climate change aspects (e.g., what is it, what affects future predictions, how it connects to current economic and production realities we live in, what actions can be taken individually and nationally, etc.), as well as the link between the climate change and social inequalities (e.g., effects of climate change on different nations, the topic of climate refugees, the occurrences when climate change introduced famines, potential for war conflicts connected to droughts in certain regions, etc.)”*

Individual or community level impacts reported by NWGs consisted of:

- Skills development of young people related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Young people acquired skills in writing a script for a video, speaking in front of the camera.”* (BE-FR)
 - *“They also learn on how to contribute to the development of their local communities through implementation of local projects and international projects.”* (PL)
- Knowledge development of young people related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Young geography students gained a better understanding of the real effects of climate change.”* (EE)
 - *“They learned about political education, the distribution of competences on different political levels and got to know opportunities to engage in the political discourse. They also learned that they have a right to participate and that their voices are important when it comes to topics that affect them, like the topic information and education about climate change and inclusion. They also got to know more youth friendly information sources when exchanging with peers about this topic.”* (AT)

- Attitude and values development of young people related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“The impact of the Training on individual level is to further motivate young people to continue to participate in decision making processes, to be able to make changes and take actions in their own local communities and schools.”* (HR)
 - *“Young people who took part in EUYD activities in Austria strengthened their citizenship. (...) and strengthened them to stand up for their demand to have more political, civic and sustainability education in school.”* (AT)
 - *“Anyone who starts to care about the environment will look out for candidates who care about the environment when electing a government and know who to vote for. This will make candidates and politicians more environmentally responsible.”* (LT)
- Activating young people towards civic and political participation endeavours and increasing the overall youth participation levels, e.g.,
 - *“Most of the youth manifested clear plans set into actions by their Organisations, and in some cases in cross-sectoral cooperation with local/regional stakeholders. Those projects are financed by EU projects and mobility projects in some cases, or from local partners and multi-collaborative groups.”* (IT)
 - *“We expect from those activities will increase youth participation local, regional and national level, so that young people will be able to implement projects with better quality on their level.”* (HU)
- Supporting sustainable choices in everyday lives of young people, e.g.,
 - *“Activities intend to go beyond information sharing and motivate and empower young people to act in favour of sustainability, either through political action or by making sustainable lifestyle choices.”* (CY)
- Strengthening disinformation resilience of young people, e.g.,
 - *“It is expected that young people will gain a more comprehensive insight and become more resilient to misleading and inaccurate information.”* (CY)
- Supporting development of youth workers related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Increase awareness among educators and youth workers of young people's needs for youth-friendly information resources and learning opportunities on this topic.”* (CZ)
 - *“Participants (youth trainers) are familiar with the process of EU dialogue with young people in the national and EU context, they acquired the knowledge, methods and tools necessary to empower young people in decision-making processes and meaningful participation, developed the ability to understand and manage group learning processes, improved the competences of the preparation and elaboration of educational content/ programmes, become familiar with the methods and tools for involving young people in the EU dialogue with young people, involved in the national database of EU youth dialogue trainers.”* (HR)
- Inspiring other stakeholders to take action related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“We hope that e.g., schools will provide more information these topics.”* (FI)

Organisational or service level impacts reported by NWGs consist of supporting:

- Organisational development of NWG members related to the sub-themes, e.g.,
 - *“The results of the consultation phase were presented and discussed thoroughly in the national working group. In the national working group, important actors from the Austrian youth field are represented, from the ministries, to representatives of the federal states, the umbrella organisation of open youth work as well as the umbrella*

organisation of youth information. All these actors benefit from the results. All organisation included in the NWG want to take criteria for youth friendly information stronger into account in their communication with young people. All organisation included in the NWG want to take criteria for youth friendly information stronger into account in their communication with young people.” (AT)

- Development of youth organisations related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“We expect from those activities that youth organisations will create a more partnerships on education and information. By their activity we expect that they will collaborate with local schools and educational institutions to create mutually beneficial partnerships that can enhance educational opportunities for young people.” (HU)*
- Development of other stakeholders capacities related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Schools are very happy with the process, and some try to implement it themselves. Because of that we started the discussion about teaching the methods to teachers.” (SI)*
- Increasing numbers of youth-friendly information sources related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Implemented activities are expected to create alternative sources and methods of youth-friendly and accessible information.” (CY)*
- Development of new tools and methodologies related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Several of our member organizations started to work on methodologies for how to work with the topic of climate change.” (SK)*
- Providing networking and peer learning opportunities related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Initiate synergies between Youth Ambassadors for the EU Youth Dialogue, young people, and the civil society such as youth clubs, youth organisations and similar actors that will work together to create a peer-to-peer learning platform or environment.” (CY)*

Policy or political level impacts reported by NWGs consist of:

- Creating opportunities for meeting and collaboration between young people and policymakers relating to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Policy makers had the opportunity to meet young people in a non-formal environment and had the time and the space to discuss with them issues that really affect their well-being.” (MT)*
 - *“As the minister was invited, a small impact was generated at political level because the minister could engage directly with young people and listen to their concerns.” (BE-DE)*
- Supporting implementation of the EU Youth Strategy
 - *“Ensure the implementation of EU Strategy 2021-2027 on national and regional level.” (HR)*
- Supporting development of participatory and deliberative approaches in policymaking, e.g.,
 - *“With every dialogue event that we organize, we feel that we contribute to normalizing this format also for politicians. Especially when it comes to aspects of education, we contribute to a mind-set, where decisions taken in this field cannot any longer be taken without engaging young people in the debate and decision-making.” (AT)*
 - *“In the context of the Presidency, the document Contribution of Non-Governmental Non-Profit Organisations to the Preparation and Implementation of the Programme*

of the Czech Presidency of the Council of the EU 2022 defined the ways in which non-profit organisations, including youth organisations, can contribute their experience and expertise to the topics of the Czech Presidency. These include, among others, the topics of sustainability and inclusiveness.” (CZ)

- Directly influencing upcoming policies related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Through the publication of our official Advice, meetings with Ministers of Education, Environment and Social inclusion should take place in the coming months. Through these meetings, we will be able to have a direct impact on current policies. Our meetings with the education federations should also lead to a reflection on the integration of the environment in the high school curriculum.” (BE-FR)*
 - *“Ireland is making a commitment to Leave No One Behind and to achieving Agenda 2030, as part of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). As part of this commitment, Ireland will present its second Voluntary National Review (VNR) of the SDGs to the UN High-Level Political Forum on Sustainable Development in July 2023. To help with this process, Participants were part of a consultation influencing policy at a European and UN level, as well as Ireland's report on the SDGs, and an animation focusing on 'Leave No One Behind'. Ireland's UN Youth Delegates were present at the event, will do up a report – a youth chapter and will take the ideas to New York in July.” (IE)*
- Creating links between youth bodies and state bodies relating to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“After speaking to the minister of Education, we got an exclusive partnership with the Flemish administration for environment. They support and develop concrete tools and websites for teachers and schools in Flanders to include sustainability in their classes (such as “Environment on School program”, “sustainable education point”, “climate on school”, etc.). In their sessions and online communication, they now include concrete tips & tricks, as mentioned in our advice.” (BE-FL)*
- Increasing accountability of policymakers related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Getting knowledge will ensure youth participation in organizing advocacy campaigns to raise awareness and to promote policy changes that support youth education and information. We are expecting that they will monitor policy changes related to youth education and information and provide feedback and recommendations to policymakers and politicians as needed.” (HU)*
- Increasing activity of state bodies relating to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“As MES sent youth recommendations to Education department to increase learning opportunities about sustainability in school agendas. MES sent EUYD results to other ministries, we received response from Ministry of Environmental Protection and Regional Development and it helped to understand what ministry is doing in frame of youth goal Nr.10.” (LV)*

2.1.2. Summary of Impacts in Action and Empowerment

The Toolkit of the 9th Cycle of the EUYD describes this subtheme as follows: *“The needs of young people should be represented at all levels of government and should enable young people to have their interests reflected in the decision-making processes. Such tools that ensure needs of future generations are taken into account in policymaking are essential especially when dealing with burning questions of today, such as the climate emergency. These tools should ensure intergenerational dialogue takes place at all times when decisions affecting more than one generation are debated and taken. Exploring*

the tools and mechanisms used in ensuring intergenerational dialogue and balance in decision-making can help provide basis on which such tools become widely used across the European countries and institutions. These can be e-tools, parliamentary or legal processes and guarantees, committees of various titles that oversee generational justice in decision-making, youth organisations conducting advocacy and many other formats. It is also crucial that these tools are transparent and in communication with young people via different channels."

Individual or community level impacts reported by NWGs consist of:

- Skills development of young people related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *"Young people gained skills and got deeply informed about youth participation in policy making."* (BE-FL)
 - *"Increase in young people's democratic self-efficacy."* (DK)
- Knowledge development of young people related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *"The young members acquired a lot of knowledge (about the possibilities of participating in decisions, the youth test, elections,) and also skills (advocacy, public speaking) they are more aware of and/or invested in the issues of participation/engagement and are more empowered (and know the existing obstacles)."* (BE-FR)
 - *"We expect youth to be more aware of the actions they can take towards empowerment and how to fully express their concerns."* (PT)
- Attitude and values development of young people related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *"At an individual level, improving the accessibility and effectiveness of the existing mechanisms will change young people's attitude to politics, effectively addressing the problem of young people's feelings of mistrust and discontent towards policymakers, the political system, and the participatory mechanisms."* (CY)
 - *"People will not be afraid to go directly to decision-makers - politicians - and to debate with them."* (LT)
- Supporting sustainable choices in everyday lives of young people, e.g.,
 - *"There are more and more young people who don't eat meat or who decide to use green travel. Of course it is difficult to say how much of this is related to this or that campaign but anyway promoting different ways of participation increases awareness of young people and will change attitudes slowly but surely."* (FI)
- Empower young people, e.g.,
 - *"Young participants had the opportunity to examine their local environment critically and make proposals to policy makers about how it could be improved. This will empower young people to take a stand on issues they feel are important and moreover they understand that there are channels they can use to voice their concerns."* (MT)
- Activating young people towards civic and political participation endeavours, e.g.,
 - *"For a lot of youngsters the convention is the first time they engage at the political level and they are often motivated to get more committed e.g. by taking part in the national Youth Parliament or by becoming a representative of their secondary school at the national school students council CNEL (Conférence Nationale des Elèves du Luxembourg)."* (LU)
- Supporting community development, e.g.,
 - *"On a community level, the initiatives can help to build stronger, more cohesive, and resilient communities."* (HU)

Organisational or service level impacts reported by NWGs consist of:

- Exploring new methods of political participation linked to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Young people have demonstrated for a stronger and more effective climate policy for years now and the result of the consultation clearly show, that most young people in Austria do not think that the demands of their generation are taken seriously, especially when it comes to climate policy. In the light of these result, more creative and unconventional methods (while still peaceful) of bringing attention to the climate crisis are perceived as a normal response to these figures.”* (AT)
 - *“Youth delegates’ engagement in the 9th cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue has contributed to the Danish Youth Council to re-evaluate the way the organisation engages with European advocacy and to start a discussion on how Danish youth can be better represented in European decision-making.”* (DK)
- Increasing expertise of youth organisations participation linked to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“On the side of Forum des Jeunes, these activities allowed us to increase our level of expertise on some topics (youth participation and empowerment) and to be perceived as an expert, or even an advisory partner to different actors (civil society, youth sector, institutions, politicians, media.”* (BE-FR)
- Increased sharing information across organisational networks related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“We had a meeting with all educational federations in Flanders, the day after our school action in Mechelen and most of them were willing to spread the existent sustainability lesson packages to their members.”* (BE-FL)
- Increased supporting for positive developments in various stakeholders linked to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Improvements for the better communication coordination, conduct and evaluation of the public consultation process by the responsible authorities.”* (CY)
- Increased supporting for synergies among various actors related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“The expected impact of the project on all the target groups is to raise awareness of the importance of participating in community activities and the importance of cooperation and creating synergies between civil and public sectors to work together to find quality solutions to existing challenges facing young people.”* (HR)
- Increased spreading good practice examples related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Organisations seeing our example are likely to make new connections with decision-makers in their communities, to seek dialogue and, once they have done so, to make the changes they want to see, together with politicians.”* (LT)

Policy or political level impacts reported by NWGs consist of:

- Influencing policymaking via policy recommendations, e.g.,
 - *“We want to make a leaflet with the main outcomes of the survey and hand it over to politicians in the GSC. the leaflet shall contain policy suggestions which politicians are encouraged to transpose in political measures in the GSC.”* (BE-DE)
 - *“We wrote a report with our demands concerning the climate policy in Belgium, signed by 50 Civil Society Organisations and handed it over to the Belgian prime Minister.”* (BE-FR)
 - *“MES in frame of European Year of Youth organised conference, where 160 participants from government institutions and youth workers took part. The focus of the conference was to look at the EUYD consultation results and to find solutions how to implement them. One working group was dedicated to this topic and two solutions*

where found. These solutions have been already implemented (such as actively inform youth about new participation possibility thanks to Municipality law in Latvia from 01.01.2023.) As one of consultation results in Latvia was to implement vote16, MES has included it in future plans to reach this goal. It is expected to start more wider consultations about vote16 in Latvia.” (LV)

- Influencing policymaking via direct contact with policymakers, e.g.,
 - “We assume that our meetings with decision-makers (Ministers) will have an impact on environmental education. (...) About the right to vote at 16, Forum des Jeunes is in contact with the office of the Minister for Democratic Renewal to create an information campaign for young people on this topic. The impact is already measurable.” (BE-FR)
 - “When young people and organisations start to discuss and go to decision-makers, then politicians will realise that these issues are relevant to young people, which will encourage them to put these issues on their political agenda and be more accountable.” (LT)
- Influencing policymaking via direct involvement in policymaking processes, e.g.,
 - “The Cyprus Youth Council contributes to the improvement of the current legal framework regarding the policy-making processes. This is a long-lasting process initiated by the Cyprus Youth Council in the framework of the discussion on the proposed bill on public consultations in the Parliamentary Committee on Legal Affairs. The proposed bill concerns the reform of the legal framework governing the process of public consultations to ensure the effectiveness of the public consultation procedure and enhance the constructive and meaningful participation of civil society in the process.” (CY)
 - “Thanks to the World of/without Youth Conference, we were approached by the Government Office to nominate young people to the Inter-Ministerial Group on Digital Education.” (CZ)
 - “Concretely, discussions were started with Parliamentarians on how young people should be involved in the work of relevant committees under the Danish Parliament. We hope to see concrete results on this in the upcoming years.” (DK)

2.1.3. Summary of Impacts in Governance

The Toolkit of the 9th Cycle of the EUYD describes this subtheme as follows: “Youth participation mechanisms often include a consultation component, but it can be difficult to see beyond the multitude of follow-up processes on the political level to ensure the results of the participatory mechanisms have been implemented, or at least taken into account. Seeing results is, nevertheless, one of the key conditions of meaningful participation, as opposed to tokenistic youthwashing in which events are only labelled as youth participatory without any follow-up processes in place, and hence with no chance of achieving any results at all. At the same time, political processes are often complex and take time, which can impair feedback and follow-up processes, making well defined structures for follow-up an important tool in this domain. Strengthening meaningful youth participation via increasing accountability of policymakers and decision-makers (e.g., by implementing well-defined follow-up processes to the participatory mechanisms) can be achieved by identifying key success factors of mechanisms leading to such accountability. In case such mechanisms cannot be identified, young people should think forward to outline how such mechanisms could look like, and in what phases of the policy process these would be most effective, in order to outline and implement them in the future.”

Individual or community level impacts reported by NWGs consist of:

- Skills, knowledge, attitudes, and values development of young people related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“When participating somewhere in the future, they are more aware of youth washing and can more clearly distinguish a quality participation mechanism from tokenism.”* (AT)
 - *“Participants of our activities learned the conditions of participation to be implemented (in particular, transparency of participation and follow-up). They learned about the risk of youth-washing during youth-policy dialogue events and learned how to critically assess the quality of an event.”* (BE-FR)
 - *“At individual level we have been training a lot of young people in advocacy, so that they know the structures and how to influence in them. And that they would also feel confident when defending their cases in the midst of experienced adults.”* (FI)
 - *“Well executed research can help to increase awareness and knowledge of youth-related issues among young people themselves. This can empower them to become more active and engaged citizens and contribute to the development of more informed and responsible decision-making processes.”* (HU)
- Promotion of useful tools and opportunities related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Our national working group members promote a model of fair governance and gender equality in the businesses and equal opportunities.”* (GR)
 - *“Promote interest and active participation in society and connectivity with the EU community and identity of youth advisory boards and school councils.”* (HR)
- Networking related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“For our EU Youth Delegates, the meetings of the national Stakeholder Group were a good opportunity to supplement and strengthen their political and organisational network within Germany and to get to know how such committees work.”* (DE)

Organisational or service level impacts reported by NWGs consist of:

- Increasing expertise of (youth) organisations related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“These activities enabled us to increase our level of expertise in advocacy and to be perceived as an essential interlocutor.”* (BE-FR)
- Supporting cooperation among different bodies in the youth field related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“The biggest change was the cooperation among regional youth councils and federal administrations.”* (BE-FL)
- Capacity building youth organisations related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Additionally, the provision of training and methodologies can enhance the capacity and skills of the organizations and services themselves, improving their ability to effectively serve and support young people.”* (HU)
- Increased levels of participation on different levels of government, e.g.,
 - *“Through active participation in youth advisory boards and school councils, young people have the opportunity to express their opinions and recommendations to decision makers. They play an active role in their local community, instead of just being passive observers.”* (HR)

Policy or political level impacts reported by NWGs consist of:

- Mainstreaming of youth matters across a range of policy areas, e.g.,
 - *“Furthermore, climate change and inclusion are good examples for topics that are not “classical youth issues” (like education or participation) but still hugely affect young people. Therefore, the cycle contributed to further mainstreaming youth participation across all policy fields. it was still beneficial to look at the results of the consultation because some aspects of participation processes that are especially relevant to young people (e.g. putting a stronger focus on follow-up of participation processes and demanding a feedback on their ideas when it comes to the implementation from decision makers) can always be improved.” (AT)*
- Introduction of new policy tools, e.g.,
 - *“Similarly, the introduction of a “youth test” will provide a guideline for public authorities and services to evaluate the effects that any new proposals may have on youth at national level.” (CY)*
- Influencing policymaking via direct involvement in policymaking processes, e.g.,
 - *“During these activities, young members of Forum des Jeunes got directly a seat at the table (at the climate tables, the cover resolution at COP, advocacy work for the official Advice on environment education), their voices directly were taken into account in the policy texts. The impact is therefore big and real since there was no intermediary, but direct contact between policy makers (Ministers) and young people.” (BE-FR)*
- Influencing policymaking via direct contact with policymakers, e.g.,
 - *“Young people want to have a say and ask questions - meeting the minister is a good way to do that. We will continue to organise meetings with ministers and other important policymakers in the format of youth dialogue. (...) Through the format of the youth dialogue, the Minister of the Environment received direct input from young people into his work. The Minister of the Environment was also able to ask questions to young people.” (EE)*
- Influencing policymaking via feedback and recommendations from young people, e.g.,
 - *“Improved communication between student governments and decision-makers, and potentially the incorporation of youth feedback into policy and decision-making processes.” (HU)*
- Influencing policymaking via taking active role in policy evaluations, e.g.,
 - *“In 2022, the Luxembourgish Government, in the field of children’s rights, adopted two national action plans. The ministry of education is currently working on the evaluation and follow-up of the measures and actions identified, where we will provide input until March 2023, and the next steps will take place in May of 2023 (reporting by the ministry). We are in the process of compiling all the focus groups and dialogue activities that had been held on inclusion (YG#3) and sustainability (YG #10) with the aim of passing them on to the political decision-makers so that the concerns of the participants can be discussed in the various committees of the Parliament.” (LU)*
- Directly influencing upcoming policies, e.g.,
 - *“After conference YouthTest implementation in Latvia has been included in Government Action Plan till 2026 and it will ensure that the needs of young people are considered in the process of developing regulatory acts; MES expects in nearer future to focus more on explaining and informing youth and giving feedback how EUYD consultations results have been implemented.” (LV)*
- Building connections between policymakers and youth field, e.g.,

- *“These kinds of discussions, if frequent enough, are great to make fruitful and lasting connections between the youth sector and decision makers. It slowly builds trust and is steadily showing that more and more politicians recognise this kind of process and the opportunities that lie in them.” (SI)*

2.1.4. Summary of Impacts in Mobility and Solidarity

The Toolkit of the 9th Cycle of the EUYD describes this subtheme as follows: *“Youth mobility and volunteering in the environmental sector can take place in many different forms: as a semester abroad, as a volunteering year in a neighbouring country, as an internship in the European Parliament, or as a work placement after the studies are over. These opportunities can enable young people to volunteer and take part in environmental initiatives, support environmental organisations or to become involved in sustainability and inclusion causes. In all those cases, it is imperative that all young people, including marginalised young people (e.g., ethnic and religious minorities, mentally or physically disadvantaged, NEETs, and many others), have equal opportunities to participate and enjoy the many advantages such mobility periods can bring to both personal and working lives. Identifying mechanisms which help marginalised young people to take part in such opportunities, makes these opportunities attractive and relevant to them, is hence key to increasing their participation in the future and contributing to positive societal development.”*

Individual or community level impacts reported by NWGs consist of:

- Increasing awareness of learning mobility opportunities, e.g.,
 - *“This cycle of the EUYD supported young people in forming and voicing their opinion in the area of mobility and solidarity (...) and provided a room to learn about mobility and solidarity and inclusive opportunities.” (AT)*
 - *“Young people acquired knowledge about different forms of non-formal youth mobility opportunities and where to find information and support and were encouraged to take part in such activities.” (DE)*
- Implementing local and regional participatory mechanisms for young people, e.g.,
 - *“In order to ensure that young people in rural areas have access to quality participation and to reduce the barriers for mobility, platform Rural Youth within Local Action Groups, a member of our NWG, have started a structured dialogue in the regions.” (CZ)*
- Increasing intergenerational solidarity, e.g.,
 - *“At the individual or community level, the impact of these initiatives could include increased solidarity and support between generations, development of positive skills, and opportunities for young people to participate in voluntary work and engage with their communities.” (HU)*
- Increasing social cohesion, e.g.,
 - *“The individuals in the rooms had wonderful and unique opportunities to experience proximity with young people who they might not normally meet or spend time with. The combination of the workshop engagement and opportunities to connect can have a profound impact on individuals which helps to shape their view of the world and to relate to the experiences and challenges that young people who are LGBT+, ethnic minority groups, religious minorities, people from rural backgrounds, people with disabilities, etc.” (IE)*

- Skills development of multipliers, e.g.,
 - *“Ambassadors developed their communication skills, event planning, organization, management, time management skills.”* (LV)
- Increasing participation in learning mobility programmes, e.g.,
 - *“At individual level, we expect that the conference will lead to an increased number of young people who take the opportunity to participate in some of the EU Youth Programs.”* (SE)

Organisational or service level impacts reported by NWGs consist of:

- Strengthening cooperation between National Agencies and youth field actors, e.g.,
 - *“Strengthening the links between the National Agency (BIJ) and the Youth Council.”* (BE-FR)
- Developing tools and methodologies to support marginalised young people, e.g.,
 - *“Development of a procedure guide/manual for not losing one's unemployment status when going on a voluntary service.”* (BE-FR)
- Supporting development of concrete learning mobility projects, e.g.,
 - *“A partner organisation very active in the field of sustainable international youth mobility received new and very concrete impulses for their work on the topic and for their communication with young people from various backgrounds.”* (DE)
- Capacity building in youth organisations related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“Improved coordination and support for young people's voluntary work, increased engagement with informal communities and organizations of young people, and the organization of local events that address both the objectives and the needs of local young people.”* (HU)
 - *“In an organisation, a person coming from another country or culture can bring in new innovative ideas, improve the language skills of the staff and many other positive things. This is what we have experienced in our office with 4 foreign volunteers here at the moment.”* (FI)
 - *“By representing the Youth Bureau in the activities, the members of the Youth Bureau deepen their knowledge, which makes the consultations, lessons, events even more interesting and strengthens the competences of each member.”* (LT)

Policy or political level impacts reported by NWGs consist of:

- Utilising consultations to influence policy related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“The results of the consultations (barriers to access to mobility programmes and young people's demands/needs) will be brought to the attention of policy-makers in the future.”* (BE-FR)
- Utilising concrete implemented projects to influence policy related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“We are expecting a positive influence on policy especially on local level. The financial support ensured youth organisations to implement projects on local levels. We are expecting from their outcome that the local decision makers will be more aware of the needs of local youths.”* (HU)
- Utilising cooperation of various youth field actors to influence policy related to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“The involvement of young people has led to the development of programmes such as Careers of Tomorrow and Skills of Tomorrow. Thanks to the cooperation of policy makers with ministries, NGOs and governmental organisations, young people have the*

opportunity to develop their careers by entering high-growth jobs, internships and paid apprenticeships. Due to the high level of interest, more and more such politically supported initiatives for young people are being developed.” (PL)

2.1.5. Summary of Impacts in Access to Infrastructure

The Toolkit of the 9th Cycle of the EUYD describes this subtheme as follows: *“When tackling climate change, infrastructure young people live in to a large extent affects their choices when it comes to sustainable living. Accessibility of public transport within as well as outside of population centres impacts how many young people rely on personal means of transportation. Presence or absence of quality cycling lanes affects how many young people will choose bike over car in their daily commute. Access to affordable, sustainable, and quality housing determines where the young people will live and how much commuting they will need to do in order to access employment, social and healthcare services, and do their shopping. Availability of shops offering local produce, again, influences the shopping choices of young people and affects sustainability of their everyday living. In order to support access of young people to such infrastructure they see as necessary for making sustainable choices, we need not only to identify the key infrastructural elements young people desire, but also explore how these elements need to work together to allow young people using the whole system towards sustainable living. Just as eco-friendly public transport that only stops at large malls with no sustainable products in stock will not allow young people to shop, eat, and consume sustainably, then building eco-friendly houses will only work if they are built at accessible places or supported by subsidies in the area of electromobility. Exploring key infrastructural elements as well as their interplay in allowing young people to live sustainably is key in making these changes happen.”*

Individual or community level impacts reported by NWGs consist of:

- Awareness rising and reflecting in order to kick-start deliberations on the topic of infrastructure, e.g.,
 - *“In this subtheme, young people could reflect on the framework conditions around them. Many young people found lots of positive aspects in this field. However, they still identified challenges that exist in their point of view. This cycle of the EUYD supported young people in forming and voicing their opinion in the area of access to infrastructure; enabled them to make informed decisions and demand better access to various kinds of infrastructure where needed.” AT*
 - *“Impact for participants would have been: informing about opportunities (such as bonus / subventions to renovate), getting inspired by good practices, showing the possibilities to make infrastructure more inclusive and child-/youth-friendly. (...) For the first activity, young people gained skills such as empathy, thinking about other references, backgrounds, brainstorming while putting yourself in a place of someone else as well as getting information about housing rules / conditions, homelessness and the consequences this brings along.” (BE-FL)*
 - *“Participants' awareness of infrastructure and sustainability proved to be very diverse. At the workshop, some people learned about what they mean by sustainability and could also learn many interesting suggestions on how to improve the sustainability of infrastructure in cities.” (CZ)*
- Development of individual knowledge and skills of multipliers relating to the sub-theme, e.g.,
 - *“One of ambassadors took part in conference working group as expert, she developed here presentation skills and deeper knowledge about infrastructure importance in*

rural regions and how youth work can be supportive to develop infrastructure for youth in rural areas.” (LV)

Organisational or service level impacts reported by NWGs consist of:

- Creating new tools and methodologies related to infrastructure, e.g.,
 - *“The aim is to design an educational “treasure hunt” game that beyond raising awareness of the EU Youth Dialogue and the EU Youth Goals, participants will have the opportunity to navigate around various green spaces and locations related to sustainability within the city where they live. (...) It will result in an increase in visits and access to green, open and public spaces, which will evince the need for development and improvement of the quality of such spaces, including access to wi-fi, public toilets and good access by public transport.” (CY)*
- Creating new approaches at the level of organisations, e.g.,
 - *“They do not want that sustainable consumption is sold as climate action because in their view, this does not go far enough. This is also important for organisations and institutions when tackling the issue of climate change with young people: When it comes to how young people can contribute to a more sustainable world, organisations and institutions should also show strategies to young people how they can engage politically for more climate action. They should not only show young people sustainable products or teach only abandonment of certain products. A combination of practicing a more conscious consumption and engaging politically for climate action would be a suitable approach in empowering young people for climate action.” (AT)*
 - *“This is a good way to encourage the implementation of changes in the organisation, where young people and children themselves figure out how to improve the sustainability of their events (e.g. arranging to collect leftover food from the camp for livestock, tips on how to reduce waste at events, thinking about the accessibility of the clubhouse, camp or other event by public transport.” (CZ)*
- Share good practice examples on sustainability and inclusion, e.g.,
 - *“In all the proposed implementation and dissemination activities all guidelines for sustainability were followed, and green practices inspired; Sustainable and ecological mobility was encouraged during all the activities. We choose all the location of the activities so that they are accessible via public transport (by bus, tram, train, or in walking distances of public transport). Also, accessibility for every young person, especially young people that require special; Assistance was considered (access for people with disability etc.)” (HR)*
- Supporting young people in project implementation, e.g.,
 - *“MES expects that results of conference will be implemented as project ideas in local municipalities (f.e. bike sharing, bike repair places) lead by youngsters and youth workers as youth initiatives. After conference participants admitted they have new ideas to implement in local municipalities.” (LV)*

Policy or political level impacts reported by NWGs consist of:

- Seeking cross-sectorial mechanisms to influence infrastructure development, e.g.,
 - *“As it was identified in the consultation phase report, the type of sustainable infrastructure called upon by young people is primarily outside the youth sector and youth policy, so our aim is to seek for sustainable development through cross sectorial participatory mechanisms.” (CY)*

- *“They demanded framework conditions, where sustainable consumption should not be an (often expansive) alternative but the new norm.” (AT)*
- *“Ministers and ministries do work together with youth organisations when they reform public space. A lot of youth councils got also the question for advice when new spatial planning is foreseen; A lot of schools have been informed on the script, in the context of the recommendation to open up playgrounds in the weekend, so youth (organisations) could make use of this space when school is closed. This practice is becoming more and more common.” (BE-FL)*
- Promoting evidence-based decision-making in relation to infrastructure, e.g.,
 - *“We expect that the political decisions will be more informed and evidence-based, as a wider range of views, recommendations, and feedback on infrastructure policy will be available.” (HU)*
- Influencing policymaking via feedback and recommendations from young people in relation to infrastructure, e.g.,
 - *“For the next months, we expect the results from the Parliament on which suggestions on YG3 from the youngsters may play a role for a follow-up or may even find their way to implementation by being considered during the policy shaping processes.” (LU)*
 - *“Ministry of Welfare in this year will make plan for equal opportunities for persons with disabilities for years 2024-2027 and admitted that some EUYD consultation recommendation might be included in this plan.” (LV)*

General Conclusions

There are some trends that can be seen throughout the implementation reports of the NWGs, and that are worth mentioning in order to deepen our understanding of impacts generated during the 9th Cycle of the EUYD across all subthemes.

Young people are generally seen as changemakers, and many activities focus on their empowerment by providing them with information sources, educational opportunities, participation opportunities, or different tools. It is also important that **young people are often seen as multipliers**, with many activities and events focusing on supporting young people in encouraging other young people to take action in various fields. Both of these approaches are well in line with the youth-centred approach of the EUYD processes.

Development of various stakeholders is also generally supported throughout the implementation activities of the NWGs. While there still is prevalence of stakeholders who can be described as “youth field actors” (e.g., youth organisations, youth departments at various levels of governments, and even ministries which oversee youth policies), there are some attempts to also include stakeholders in cross-sectoral cooperations, such as various ministries or organisations which deal primarily with different topics out of the typical youth field scope (e.g., infrastructure, sustainability). Cross-sectoral cooperation and development of actors beyond the youth field domain can be seen as an important step for the EUYD processes in general, as reaching some of the Youth Goals might be impossible without cooperation with such actors. In this case, we can also talk about **initiation or development of stakeholder networks** with high potential to create impact in the future as they not only bring together key players with power in various key subdomains (e.g., infrastructure, health, environment, etc.), but also allows them to develop their capacities in synchrony with each other. This suggests increase in their potential to cooperate on creating solutions for complex problems they would not be able to tackle as standalone actors, and which would be hard to solve without well-functioning relationships among the stakeholders (e.g., youth organisations, various ministries, partners from other fields, etc.).

In some cases, **direct or indirect influence over a development of policies** can be seen, and such steps can be seen as important developments that also shape democracies in Europe. Such democracy shaping takes place not only on the part of the young people and youth organisations who learn how to communicate with policymakers, but notably also on the part of policymakers who learn how to use information, processes, and structures which involve young people to create high-quality policies. **Mainstreaming of youth topics** is also present, again showcasing how complex matters are (starting to be) taken into account by stakeholders from different fields.

Utilization of **evidence-based approaches** is also one of the trends, be it in the form of implementing research methods directly (e.g., by implementing or commissioning specific research by NWGs and other actors), or by emphasizing youth information as one of the key domains in which impacts are described. This trend brings in potential to strengthen all abovementioned ones by creating basis for sound argumentation, targeted action, and increased accountability of policymakers and decisionmakers. The capacities to monitor and evaluate impacts are therefore among those which ought to be boosted in youth field actors, including NWGs, in order to further support the evidence-based approaches.

Reports of the NWGs also showed **uneven levels of attention to various sub-themes** of the 9th Cycle of the EUYD. This can be seen in missing sub-theme reporting in some of the NWGs reports (e.g., some NWGs explicitly deciding on not covering certain sub-themes), but also in different levels of details submitted in each sub-theme. Despite attempts to reach out to actors beyond the youth field domain

as mentioned above, most of the described impacts are still closely linked to the youth policy and youth field domains, with limited overlap with, for example, the domain of infrastructure.

It should also be stressed, that **EUYD generated impacts are still being created**, and will continue to be created in near and far future. This is linked to the timeframe of the EUYD processes which are restricting the amount, size, and detectability of impacts generated at this time of the overall process (namely before the last EUYC of the current Trio). Being aware of this quality of the EUYD also helps set the impacts collected by the NWGs into a proper context and understand why some of the listed impacts are assumed, declared, or future-oriented ones. Lastly, it is sometimes difficult to see what impacts listed by the NWGs are truly linked to the 9th Cycle of the EUYD, which are perhaps linked to previous EUYD cycles, and which are synchronous processes contributing to currently tackled topics, but nonetheless running independently of the EUYD processes. While complexity of current topics is one of the reasons behind this ambiguity, further debates on what impacts are to be monitored and measured in the future, might help NWGs to collect more targeted evidence in the future.